

Research Organization Registry

organization ID for research institutions

Research Organization Registry (ROR)

ROR is an open registry maintained by the research community for organizational IDs and metadata of research institutions worldwide.

ROR is non-commercial and assigns the ROR ID as a persistent identifier exclusively for organizations that conduct, fund, and publish research.

ROR ID focuses on the persistent affiliation of research output and scholars with research institutions, even when name and language variants of the organizations exist.

ROR ID is internationally acknowledged by publishers, repositories and research institutions.

Persistent identifiers

and are trademarks of the Int. DOI Fd.

How ROR ID works

Each ROR ID represents an individual alphanumeric identifier → e.g. 02h2x0161

ROR IDs are static and link via a URL to the organizations' individual entries in the ROR registry.

Typical presentation on web pages or in PDFs of research articles:

- ① <https://ror.org/02h2x0161> → URL of the individual ROR entry
- ② GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel → Name and ROR logo with link to individual ROR entry

ROR ID metadata

Registered ROR IDs are linked to base metadata of the respective research organization:

- name, name variants, language variants, acronyms, relations to other facilities, type, status, address, GeoName, etc.
- alternative IDs of the organization (Crossref Funder ID, GRID, ISNI, Wikidata)
- URL of the organization and, if applicable, of the Wikipedia website, e-mail address, IP address

ROR identifiers and metadata are CC0 licensed and are freely retrievable and reusable:

- (creative commons, public domain)
- accessible via search interface (ror.org/search), open REST API and public data dump on Zenodo

ROR ID integration

ROR ID is integrated into the metadata schemes of:

ROR ID registration and curation

New ROR IDs and modifications of existing IDs can be applied free of charge at ror.org/curation.

Maintenance of metadata of registered research institutions is done by an international committee of the research community:

- ensuring consistency and integrity of the registry
- updating the registry on a monthly basis

Advantages of the ROR ID for scientific publications

- ① clear identification of affiliations even in case of name and language variations of the research institutions
- ② active, interoperable and sustainable link to research institutions
- ③ inclusion of ROR IDs in publication metadata alongside other persistent identifiers (DOI, ORCID and Crossref Funder ID)
- ④ simplified tracking of the publication output of research institutions

Please cite as:

Boxhammer, Tim & Mehrtens, Hela. (2023). Factsheet | ROR – organization ID for research institutions. Zenodo. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8178750](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8178750)

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 DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8178750](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8178750)

